

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

**SUstainable Management of soil Organic Matter to
Mitigate Trade-offs between C sequestration and
nitrous oxide, methane and nitrate losses**

Deliverable 6.4

Report of the results from questionnaires

Due date of deliverable: M26
Actual submission date: 22.03.2023

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Project title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	6.4
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Report of the results from questionnaires
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP6
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Participatory Action Research, Communication and Dissemination
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	CREA
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DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.14169742
LICENSE	CC BY 4.0
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	PU

ABSTRACT

The SOMMIT project promotes the adoption of virtuous soil management strategies (SMSs), their experimentation and rapid innovation by relying on the consortium's long-term experiments (LTEs). This goal is promoted by setting up Living Labs, characterized by a biophysical component (the LTEs themselves) and a social component. The social component consists of farmers, technicians and representatives of farmer associations, who are engaged in the evaluation and testing of the SMSs considered in the project and the design of the LTEs. In this Deliverable, the first steps were taken toward the definition of new LLs in three of the partner countries participating in the project. To achieve this goal, a questionnaire was designed and distributed to a previously identified stakeholder platform, SP (i.e., a list of potentially interested stakeholders). The SP was queried for awareness of the impact of management choices on climate change, research ambitions on the interaction between land management and climate, and interest in and knowledge of the SMSs tested in the LTE. The questionnaire was distributed in local language to the SPs in Italy, Poland and Spain. A total of 66 stakeholders (60% farmers) joined the initiative, and most respondents (68%) expressed willingness to participate in the SMS testing activity, as well as confirmed interest in practices already implemented in the LTEs.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

GHG: Greenhouse gasses

LLs: Living Labs

LTE: Long term experiment

SMSs: Soil Management Strategies

SOM: Soil Organic Carbon

SP: Stakeholders' platform

1. Introduction & Context

Through the new “European Green Deal”, the European Commission focused on EU agricultural sector stewardship of the environment through its Farm to Fork (F2F), Biodiversity 2030 and Zero Pollution strategies, setting policy targets for 2030 and 2050 for sustainable food systems, from production to consumption. The mitigation of climate change is one of the priorities, with an increasing focus on the implementation of agricultural practices which contribute to soil C sequestration (Cseq) to mitigate rising atmospheric CO₂ levels. Moreover, territoriality and control at the local level play a pivotal role in promoting the design of higher sustainability and resilience of the food systems, allowing the identification of tailor-made re-design strategies through the direct involvement of local stakeholders in the process. In this context, the SOMMIT project aims to promote the adoption of virtuous SMSs their testing and fast innovation relying on the LTE of the consortium and the setting up of LLs (*“Living Labs are defined as user-centered, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings”* (European networks of living labs - <https://enoll.org/>)) around the LTEs the same (D6.3). Once defined the biophysical (at the beginning the only LTE, to be collaborated with on-farm trials) and social (the stakeholder platform SP) dimensions of the living lab, a Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodological approach is used to collaborate with the local communities (SP) to reach a clear understanding of the role, assets and skills of researchers and other actors throughout an iterative interaction, according to a long-range, cyclical, self-correcting mechanism, following a simple four-step model (plan, act, observe, and reflect, according to the Action Research Spiral).

2. Methodology

To activate the LL a modified “participation by consultation” approach was followed, in which the SP was consulted with a questionnaire to identify the perception of the research demand and the consequent objectives to be implemented in the LL. Moreover, it was used to test the effective interest of local stakeholders about the main tasks carried out in the LTE, providing useful information for potential revision of the experimental plan, to increase the correspondence with the social context of the territory in which the LTEs are embedded. The questionnaire results are then ready to be discussed with the SP in first face-to-face meeting to allow a deeper understanding of results, a prioritization of the research needs and facilitate the debate on available SMS connected with climate change mitigation. The questionnaire was composed of 16 questions divided into 9 sections, namely: i) profiling; ii) awareness of the impact of management choices on climate change; iii) interest to SMSs; iv) ambitions on the research on soil management-climate interaction; v) interest on the practices tested in the LTE; vi) knowledge on available SMSs; vii) Interest to test; viii) perception of the benefit of participatory activity; ix) self-efficacy. The questionnaire was distributed to the SPs in local language in Italy, Poland, Spain, Austria, and Slovenia. The questionnaires shared the same questions for each section but the v) one, in which the questions were tailor-made to the specific layout and objectives of each LTE.

3. Relevant findings

The questionnaire was distributed within the SPs previously identified (D6.3) and a total of XX questionnaires were completed and collected (table 1). GENERAL CONSIDERATION, GENDER ASPECTS, SIMILAR RESULTS, CROSS-CUTTING ISSUES – TO BE WRITTEN ONCE COLLECTED RESULTS FROM AUSTRIA AND SLOVENIA. HERE THE PERCEPTION OF PARTICIPATORY ACTIVITY SHOULD BE ADDED.

Table 1. Questionnaire by typology of actors collected during the survey.

	Italy	Poland	Spain	Total
Farmers	12	28	2	42
Technicians	6	3	5	14
Farm association	1	2	3	6
Others	1	0	3	4
Total	18	33	13	66

Most of the respondents expressed their willingness in participation to test (XX % in Austria; 89% in Italy; 60 % in Poland; XX& in Slovenia; 67% in Spain). As far as the LTE evaluation was concerned the SPs showed interest for the tested practices. These results (not shown in this report) are argument of debate between the SOMMIT researchers, the LTE managers, and the SPs the same, to better understand the local priorities and adapt, whenever possible, the LTE with the suggestions/comments and point of view raised with the discussion.

3.1 Italy

Italian SP was composed by 12 farmers (mainly organic farms), 6 technicians (two of whom also declared their role as farmers), 1 Farm association and 1 social cooperative (others), for a total of 18 answers. The SP shared a high level of concern about the effects of climate change with the 89% answering 'yes' on the relative question. The 100% of answerers declared to agree with the statements that agricultural land management practices “have an impact on carbon sequestration” and “may be linked to GHG emission” (data not shown). Moreover, the 18% of respondents agreed with the potential reduction of system productivity when soil strategies to increase soil organic matter are implemented (Figure 3.2.1).

Figure 3.2.1 – awareness of Italian SP on the climate change impact of soil management strategies.

The interest of better understand the relationship between soil management practices and their effects on climate change characterised the 95% of the respondents who declare to be very (65%) or quite (29%) interested in having more choices for soil management practices (data not shown).

In the Italian SP perception soil management practices to address climate change should (Figure 3.2.2a): exclude deep tillage (44%), optimized through innovation of mechanization (new tools/machines) (39%), be realized reducing fuel consumption (33%), be reduced in number (22%). Moreover, the SP totally agreed (50%) or agreed (33%) on the belief that “research should give priority to new and improved soil management practices addressed to reduce the impact of climate change on the environment” (figure 3.2.2b)

Figure 3.2.2 – ambitions of Italian SP on how soil management strategies should be improved to address the climate change issue.

In Table 3.2.1, the preferences on which practices related to increase/preservation of SOM, the ones potential useful with this aim but not convenient from an economic point of view, and the ones fundamental to reduce GHG emissions from soils are reported. The reduced tillage was perceived as the most effective for both SOM increase/preservation and GHG reduction and one with lower impact on the economic sustainability. Zero tillage was recognized as very impacting on GHG emission and very low affecting the SOM protection. On the other hand, compost was considered on of the practices less viable for economic point of view although effective on SOM and GHG, followed in the same trajectory by crop rotation. Incorporation of crop residues and manure/slurry use where positively considered about their effect on SOM but 31% and 38% indicated these practices with some economic levels for crops residues and manure/slurry incorporations, respectively.

Table 3.2.1 Italian SP perception of the SMSs considered in the SOMMIT project

	Practices fundamental to preserve and/or increase the soil organic matter (%; n=16)	Practices useful to preserve and/or increase the soil organic matter but not convenient from an economic point of view (%; n=13)	Practices useful to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (%; n=15)
zero tillage	6	23	47
Reduced tillage	56	15	60
Incorporation of crop residues	50	31	7
cover crops	38	15	20
crop rotation	38	31	27
manure/slurry	25	38	7
compost	44	46	27
Biochar	6	8	0
Others	13	23	7

Finally, the self-efficacy questions showed an Italian SP from partially sure (44%), sure (28%) or absolutely sure (11%) to be able to choose soil management practices with low impact on climate change (Figure 3.2.3a). On the other hand, the respondents declared to totally disagree (11%), disagree (11%) or neither disagree nor agree (17%) to be able to use of soil management practices able to reduce the effects on climate change if they involve obtaining agricultural subsidies (Figure 3.2.3b).

Figure 3.2.3 – Italian SP self-efficacy on the ability to choose SMSs with reduced or low impact on climate change.

3.2 Poland

Polish SP was composed by 28 farmers, 3 technicians (advisors), and 2 Farm association representatives, for a total of 33 answers.

The Polish SP showed a high awareness about the impact of climate change on the planet (82%), with 75% of respondents declaring to consider the potential impact of its own actions before making decisions (figure 3.3.1a). The 30% of respondents agreed with the potential reduction of system productivity when soil strategies to increase soil organic matter are implemented, whereas a 63% disagreed with this statement (Figure 3.3.1b).

Figure 3.3.1 – awareness of Polish SP on the climate change impact of soil management strategies.

The interest of better understand the relationship between soil management practices and their effects on climate change characterised the 67% of the respondents who declare to be very (30%) or quite (52%) interested in having more choices for soil management practices (data not shown).

In the Polish SP perception soil management practices to address climate change should (Figure 3.3.2a): optimized through innovation of mechanization (new tools/machines) (45%), be reduced in number (22%), be diversified over time to minimize the soil disturbance (15%), exclude deep tillage (6%), be realized reducing fuel consumption (6%). Moreover, the SP agreed (18%) or totally agreed (73%) on the belief that “research should give priority to new and improved soil management practices addressed to reduce the impact of climate change on the environment” (figure 3.3.2b)

Figure 3.3.2 – ambitions of Polish SP on how soil management strategies should be improved to address the climate change issue.

The Polish SP considered the manure/slurry use and the cover crop introduction as the most effective practices to preserve and increase the SOM (73 and 70%, respectively) even if with a perceived economic cost (48 and 30%, respectively) as reported in table 3.3.1. On the other hand, zero tillage (79%) and reduced tillage (67%) were considered as the most effective on GHG emission reduction with a lower cost perception (21 and 9%, respectively).

Table 3.3.1 Polish SP perception of the SMSs considered in the SOMMIT project

	Practices fundamental to preserve and/or increase the soil organic matter (%; n=33)	Practices useful to preserve and/or increase the soil organic matter but not convenient from an economic point of view (%; n=33)	Practices useful to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (%; n=33)
zero tillage	6	21	79
Reduced tillage	12	9	67
Incorporation of crop residues	55	12	6
cover crops	70	36	9
crop rotation	30	6	9
manure/slurry	73	48	12
compost	21	30	9
Biochar	0	45	9
Others	0	6	0

When considering its self-efficacy, the Polish SP a 52% and a 27% of respondents declared to be sure or partially sure to be confident to choose soil management with low impact on climate change (figure 3.3.3), whereas the 52 % and 45% totally agreed or agreed with an increase use of SMSs with a low effect on climate change if they involve obtaining agricultural subsidies.

Figure 3.3.3 – Polish SP self-efficacy on the ability to choose SMSs with reduced or low impact on climate change.

3.3 Spain

Spanish SP was composed by 2 farmers, 5 technicians (including advisors), 3 Farm association representatives, 2 representatives of fertilizer company for a total of 9 answers.

The 100% of the SP shared high concern about the effects of climate change, agreeing (56%) or totally agreeing in considering the potential impact of its own actions before making decisions. The 78% of answerers declared to agree with the statements that agricultural land management practices “have an impact on carbon sequestration” and “may be linked to GHG emission” (data not shown). Moreover, the 11% of respondents agreed with the potential reduction of system productivity when soil strategies to increase soil organic matter are implemented, whereas a 67% and 11% disagreed and strongly disagreed with this statement (Figure 3.5.1).

Figure 3.5.1 – awareness of Spanish SP on the climate change impact of soil management strategies.

The interest of better understand the relationship between soil management practices and their effects on climate change characterised the 100% of the respondents who declare to be very (67%) or quite (33%) interested in having more choices for soil management practices (data not shown).

In the Spanish SP perception soil management practices to address climate change should (Figure 3.5.2): optimized through innovation of mechanization (new tools/machines) (67%), be reduced in number (55%), be realized reducing fuel consumption (44%), be diversified over time to minimize the soil disturbance (33%), exclude deep tillage (33%), consider other solutions (44%). Moreover, the SP agreed (67%) or totally agreed (33%) on the belief that “research should give priority to new and improved soil management practices addressed to reduce the impact of climate change on the environment” (data not shown)

Figure 3.5.2 – ambitions of Spanish SP on how soil management strategies should be improved to address the climate change issue.

According to Spanish stakeholders, the incorporation of crop residues was the most effective practice on SOM increase/preservation (78%) with a low economic cost (11%) and a medium impact on GHG emission (33%). Manure/slurry and compost application were also recognized as effective on SOM (67% and 56% of preferences, respectively) and a moderately low economic cost (22% both) and a low (22% for compost) or absent (manure/slurry) impact on GHG emission reduction. Cover crops were indicated for both GHG emission reduction (56%) and SOM preservation (44) but also a medium-high economic cost (44%).

Table 3.5.1 Spanish SP perception of the SMSs considered in the SOMMIT project

	Practices fundamental to preserve and/or increase the soil organic matter (%; n=9)	Practices useful to preserve and/or increase the soil organic matter but not convenient from an economic point of view (%; n=9)	Practices useful to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (%; n=9)
zero tillage	33	22	89
Reduced tillage	0	0	0
Incorporation of crop residues	78	11	33
cover crops	44	44	56
crop rotation	33	22	11
manure/slurry	67	22	0
compost	56	22	22
Biochar	22	11	33
Others	0	0	22

The answers referring to self-efficacy showed a Spanish SP from totally sure (44%) and sure (33%) to be able to choose soil management practices with low impact on climate change (Figure 3.5.3a). The respondents declared to agree (67%), totally agree (22%) or neither disagree nor agree (11%) to be able to use of soil management practices able to reduce the effects on climate change if they involve obtaining agricultural subsidies (Figure 3.5.3b).

Figure 3.5.3 – Spanish SP self-efficacy on the ability to choose SMSs with reduced or low impact on climate change.

a

b

